

Albania's ERA Integration

Progress and recommendations

Progress

Structural reforms in the research sector

- Reinforcement of R&I as part of the Economic Recovery Plan 2021–2023
- Publication of Research Infrastructure Roadmap for Albania by the Regional Cooperation Council (2022)
- Progress in design of the Smart Specialisation Strategy
- New strategies and regulations in place to promote innovation, particularly for SMEs

Internationalisation activities

- Mutual recognition of higher education diplomas with partners in the region
- Significant increase in participation in COST Actions
- Joining EUREKA
- Launch of EURAXESS profile
- Participation in the European Innovation Scoreboard 2022 and She Figures 2021

Gender equality

- Current Albanian government with highest share of women in the world
- 62% of women among doctoral graduates (She Figures 2021)
- 4.3% female graduates in science, technology, engineering and mathematics compared to 2.8% male graduates (2021)

Future support for R&I

- Competitive allocation of institutional funding for centres of excellence from 2025 onwards
- Building of Science and Technology Parks
- Establishment of a platform for the promotion of Open Science in 2023

Recommendations

Establish a comprehensive approach regarding R&I

- Provide a better R&I framework and coordinate at governmental, institutional and researcher level to improve research output
- Enhance structured planning for implementation of the new Law of Science and the National Strategy for Research, Technology and Innovation 2023-2027
- Improve coordination to increase the effectiveness of the Smart Specialisation Strategy development
- Establish active participation in ERA meetings and engage in the new European Innovation Agenda

Improve research conditions

- Provide professional support for applicants to further increase participation in European projects (COST, Horizon Europe, EUREKA)
- Establish peer-review evaluation for project applications within research calls
- Introduce an Open Access strategy with a legal framework

Support research infrastructure

- Ensure funding of research facilities, labs and infrastructures to safeguard research activity
- Start participation in European Research Infrastructure Consortia

Improve cooperation of the higher education and the private sector

- Design a vision for knowledge valorisation and technology transfer to better connect research performing organisations with the productive sector
- Create an adequate meeting space for companies and researchers
- Increase the collaboration between higher education and the private sector, especially in science, technology, engineering and mathematics

